

Corrigendum to

“N : P stoichiometry and habitat effects on Mediterranean savanna seasonal root dynamics” published in Biogeosciences, 16, 1883–1901, 2019

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Published: 31 July 2019

In the manuscript we did not correctly provide the statement of funding required by the main project funder.

The entire acknowledgement section should be replaced with the following:

Acknowledgements. This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement no. 748893. A Marie Skłodowska-Curie Individual Fellowship was awarded to Richard K. F. Nair and the field site was also funded via the Alexander von Humboldt Foundation and Max Planck Society research prize to Markus Reichstein. We acknowledge the invaluable field support of Enrique Juarez, Andrew Durso and Jinhong Guan as well as Mónica Lorente, Fatima Khalid and Rolf Rödiger, who assisted in laboratory processing of root samples. We are also especially grateful to Gianluca Fillipa for sharing his expertise in interactive GUIs for graphics processing in R.

The article processing charges for this open-access publication were covered by the Max Planck Society.